

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CRYPTOCOCCAL INFECTION IN HIV/AIDS PATIENTS

Mînzătean N.,

*student, Faculty of General Medicine, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu"
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Iarovoi L.,

scientific supervisor, associate professor, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu" Republic of Moldova, Chisinau

Nagiț A.

*Head of ARV treatment and palliative care department
in the Dermatological and Communicable Diseases Hospital Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Abstract

An important infectious illness for worldwide public health is cryptococcosis. According to estimates, the primary risk factor for 95% of cases in middle- and low-income countries and 80% of cases in high-income nations is HIV infection [1]. Patients are addressed in the late stages of HIV/AIDS infection, the cause of referral to the hospital being concomitant infections that have occurred. One of the most dangerous illnesses connected to HIV/AIDS patients is cryptococcal infection. Damage to the brain and the lungs is one of the leading causes of mortality. As a result, individuals get cryptococcal encephalitis, meningitis, or pulmonary cryptococcosis.

On the basis of a database of 17 patients registered at the Dermatological and Communicable Diseases Hospital (SDMC), Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, a study was done to examine the epidemiology, clinical course, and contemporary ways of treating Cryptococcal infection. People aged 36 to 45 make up the majority of those with this diagnosis (47%). Men are slightly more likely than women to get cryptococcal infection.

Keywords: Cryptococcosis, Cryptococcus neoformans, HIV/AIDS infection

Introduction

Cryptococcosis is an infectious disease caused by the yeast fungus *Cryptococcus neoformans* of the Basidiomycota phylum [2], refers to deep mycoses. *Cryptococcus* is not a representative of the normal human microflora; its isolation always indicates a clinically pronounced or subclinical infection (including in people without immune disorders). *C. neoformans* is one of the main causes of CNS lesions in patients with immunodeficiency. In patients with HIV infection, especially in Europe and America, *C. neoformans* var. *neoformans* is mainly isolated.

The natural source of *C. neoformans* var. *neoformans* is soil containing pigeon droppings, less often rotting vegetables, fruits, plants. Human infection from animals, as well as the transmission of the pathogen from human to human (except in cases of transplantation of infected organs) have not been proven. The main route of transmission is airborne dust, infection through damaged skin or mucous membranes is possible. Most often, the entrance gate of infection is light. Cryptococci that have penetrated into the lungs (usually small capsule-free forms that reach the alveoli) create a primary focus of infection, from where pathogens are spread hematogenically to various organs and tissues. There is evidence that in people without immune disorders, cryptococci can remain inactive in the lungs indefinitely, and activation of latent infection occurs only under unfavorable conditions [10].

The incubation period of the disease ranges from several days to several months. Clinical manifestations of the disease depend on the localization of lesions and the severity of immunodeficiency. The most common clinical form of cryptococcosis is meningitis (up to

90% of all cases of cryptococcosis) [9], which develops in 2.0–7.5% of AIDS patients. The disease is usually generalized, except for the central nervous system, the pathogen often affects the lungs and skin, less often other organs (bone marrow, lymph nodes, liver, kidneys, adrenal glands, joints, myocardium, pericardium, spleen). Cryptococcal meningitis is the most common fungal lesion of the central nervous system in HIV infection. Approximately 50% of HIV-infected patients suffering from cryptococcal meningitis develop cryptococcal pneumonia [1],[3]. Cases of asymptomatic course of the disease are described.

Cryptococcal infection in individuals with normal immune status proceeds benign and in many cases self-eliminated, being detected mainly during preventive radiological examination in the form of residual phenomena in the lungs. The exception is cryptococcal meningitis, which, with untimely diagnosis and treatment, ends in death, or leaves residual changes. Risk factors for the development of cryptococcosis: immunodeficiency conditions associated with HIV infection, prolonged use of glucocorticoids and immunosuppressors, organ and tissue transplantation, some hemoblastoses (acute lymphoblastic leukemia, lymphoma). People with decompensated diabetes mellitus, hepatic and renal insufficiency, sarcoidosis, collagenoses are also at risk of the disease.

Aim of the study

Study of the epidemiology, clinical aspects, laboratory changes and modern methods of treatment of cryptococcal infection in HIV/AIDS patients.

Materials and methods

The study included 17 patients diagnosed with cryptococcal infection, registered at the Dermatological

and Communicable Diseases Hospital from 2018 to 2022. A retrospective method of statistical research was used. To fill in statistical questionnaires, data from medical records of patients observed in the outpatient clinic were used: gender, age of patients, clinical signs and examination data, laboratory tests, bone marrow aspirates, treatment methods depending on the stage. The clinical diagnosis was made based on the clinical picture of the patient, CD4 levels (low), lumbar puncture (inclusive with microscopic identification of C.

neoformans in cerebrospinal fluid), biochemistry, blood culture, chest X-ray, CT or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain.

The study involved 17 patients who were hospitalized during 2018-2022 including 5 women and 12 men, the average age being 46 years. Most patients were aged 36-45 (47%), followed by 46-55 (17%), and those aged 26-35, 56-65 and 66-75 had 12% each (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Distribution of patients according to age

Results

Thirteen patients were discovered to be Stage C3 at the time of presenting patients to the hospital.

It should also be noted that all patients who initiated TARV have abandoned it and are currently not compliant with treatment. Therefore, this is one of the causes of the progression of the disease.

Out of 17 cases of cryptococcal infection in HIV/AIDS patients, 7 cases were found to be fatal.

Laboratory data confirmed the severity of the patients' health status, so in 7 of the patients CD4 levels were within the limits of 0 to 10, CD4 levels between 11-20 and 61-70 in 3 patients; 51-60 – 2 patients and more than 100 in one person (Figure 2). In the retrospective study, 16 patients were sexually infected and one patient intravenously (drugs). This fact confirms that the most common route of HIV infection is sexual.

Figure 2. CD4 levels recorded to HIV/AIDS patients

In the course of research, we found that the most common form of cryptococcal damage is cerebral (50%), followed by pulmonary (18%), disseminated (18%) and cutaneous (14%) Cryptococcosis (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Types of clinical forms of Cryptococcal infection found in HIV/AIDS patients

The clinical picture of patients is very varied and includes a spectrum of concomitant pathologies. Patients complain headache, nausea, fever, altered consciousness, cranial neuropathy, memory loss, confusion, signs of meningeal irritation, nausea and vomiting, seizures, visual and hearing impairment, confusion, abnormal mental state and lethargy.

The most common comorbidities are represented by candida albicans (present in all patients). Followed

by hepatitis (8 patients), pulmonary pathology (7 patients), kidney pathology (5 patients). Two patients suffered from syphilis. It was detected that one patient had cerebral toxoplasmosis, one had non-hodjkin lymphoma, and one had cardiac pathology. Three patients each had Herpes simplex, three -encealopathy, three-meningitis, three- cachexia, and three- tuberculosis (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Comorbidities present in HIV/AIDS patients

All patients were treated in the Dermatological and Communicable Diseases Hospital (SDMC) in the ARV treatment and palliative care department. However, patients with serious disease evolution were admitted to the Department of intensive therapy. Fluconazole was the major medication used to treat cryptococcal infection. Patients were given fluconazole in the form of tablets 150 mg per oral or solution 2mg/ml intravenously. The drug was administered during the entire period of hospitalization of the patient. Antibiotics and vitamin complexes were utilized to treat the patients co-infections. The drug-dependent patient also received Methadones hydrochloride 5 mg/ml for 7 days. In patients with CD4 level >10 and less than 3 comorbidities, are noted to improve health after receiving treatment with fluconazole. However, in the case of patients with low CD4 level (below 10) and who suffers from multiple (more than 4) comorbidities (hepatitis,

tuberculosis, syphilis, gonorrhoea ,etc.) a lethal end was attested (7 patients).

Discussion

A poor outlook for the patient's health might result from a number of factors, including delayed treatment, the existence of multiple concurrent disorders, and non-compliance with TARV. The age group that is most susceptible to a cryptococcal infection is between the ages of 36 and 45 (47%). Men are more likely to experience an incident than women are.

The portal of entry of Cryptococcus is usually through inhalation of spores or desiccated yeast cells from the environment. Therefore, immunocompromised people such as HIV/AIDS patients are vulnerable to Cryptococcus infection. Another factor contributing to the infection's severity is Cryptococcus neoformans' predilection for the central nervous system and

ability to cross the blood-brain barrier. The most serious consequences are meningitis and meningoencephalitis which can lead to death.

Despite the patient's severe degree of illness upon admission, CD4 level below 100, and the existence of concomitant diseases that were connected with it, TARV was successful in 10 out of 17 cases.

Conclusion

From the case of 17 diagnosed patients with HIV and opportunistic infection of *Cryptococcus neoformans* that is presented above, it can be seen that mortality in HIV-infected patients with cryptococcus is high. Antiretroviral therapy in HIV-infected patients should begin as soon as the patient is admitted in the hospital. The successful treatment of HIV with cryptococcosis requires the use of antifungal treatments, intracranial pressure management for cryptococcal meningitis, and the administration of ARVs to restore immunological function.

References

- HOLBAN, T., PLĂCINTĂ, Gh., COJOCARU, S., IAROVUI, L., CEBĂTORESCU, V. Ghid practic Infecția cu HIV: ETIOLOGIE, PATOGENIE, TABLOU CLINIC, DIAGNOSTIC, TRATAMENT, Chișinău 2011 <https://library.usmf.md/ro/library/boli-infectioase/holban-t-placinta-gh-cojocaru-s-iarovoi-l-cebatorescu-v-infecția-cu-hiv>
- Bîstrițchi, I., HOLBAN, T., COJOCARU, S., MICȘANSCHI, P. Tratatamentul antiretroviral în infecția cu HIV/SIDA. Chișinău 2019
- Gushiken, A. C., Saharia, K. K., & Baddley, J. W. (2021). Cryptococcosis. *Infectious Disease Clinics of North America*, 35(2), 493–514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idc.2021.03.012>
- Nowak, M. A., Putynkowska, A., Barańska-Rybak, W., Czarnacka, K., & Dębska-Ślizień, M. A. (2020). Cutaneous cryptococcosis: an underlying immunosuppression? Clinical manifestations, pathogenesis, diagnostic examinations and treatment. *Postepy Dermatologii i Alergologii*, 37(2), 154–158. <https://doi.org/10.5114/ada.2020.94833>
- Zhang, Y., Cooper, B., Gui, X., Sherer, R., & Cao, Q. (2019). Correction: Clinical diversity of invasive cryptococcosis in AIDS patients from central China: Report of two cases with review of literature (*BMC Infectious Diseases* (2019) 19 (1003) DOI: 10.1186/s12879-019-4634-7). *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 19(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-019-4698-4>
- Spec, A., & Powderly, W. G. (2018). Cryptococcal meningitis in AIDS. In *Handbook of Clinical Neurology* (1st ed., Vol. 152). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63849-6.00011-6>
- Toivonen, A., Eriksson, M., Friberg, N., Hautala, T., Kääriäinen, S., Leppäaho-Lakka, J., Mikkola, J., Nieminen, T., Oksi, J., Salonen, J. H., Suomalainen, P., Vääntinen, M., Jarva, H., & Jääskeläinen, A. J. (2021). Clinical characteristics and evaluation of the incidence of cryptococcosis in Finland 2004–2018. *Infectious Diseases*, 53(9), 684–690. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23744235.2021.1922753>
- Srichatrapimuk, S., & Sungkanuparph, S. (2016). Integrated therapy for HIV and cryptococcosis. *AIDS Research and Therapy*, 13(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12981-016-0126-7>
- Olanrewaju, F. O., Oripelaye, M. M., & Ariyibi, O. O. (2018). Cutaneous cryptococcosis in HIV patient: A diagnostic dilemma. *HIV and AIDS Review*, 17(2), 142–145. <https://doi.org/10.5114/hivar.2018.76377>
- Alaniz, A. J., Carvajal, J. G., Carvajal, M. A., Cogliati, M., & Vergara, P. M. (2020). Spatial Quantification of the Population Exposed to *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Cryptococcus gattii* Species Complexes in Europe: Estimating the Immunocompetent and HIV/AIDS Patients Under Risk. *Risk Analysis*, 40(3), 524–533. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.13410>
- Onyishi, C. U., & May, R. C. (2022). Human immune polymorphisms associated with the risk of cryptococcal disease. *Immunology*, 165(2), 143–157. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imm.13425>
- Panel on Opportunistic Infections in Adults, T. (2022). Guidelines for the Prevention and Treatment of Opportunistic Infections in Adults and Adolescents with HIV. Office of AIDS Research Advisory Council (OARAC), C1. http://aidsinfo.nih.gov/content-files/lvguidelines/adult_oi.pdf. Accessed
- Parker, N., Strong, N., Pichetsurthorn, P., Lulich, D., & Moore, T. (2020). Disseminated Sporotrichosis With Brain Abscesses in an HIV-Infected Patient. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.8016>
- Jehangir, W., Tadepalli, G. S., Sen, S., Regevik, N., & Sen, P. (2015). Coccidioidomycosis and Blastomycosis: Endemic Mycotic Co-Infections in the HIV Patient. *Journal of Clinical Medicine Research*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.14740/jocmr2036w>